

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

D2.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

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R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

Researchers prepare at least one R&I publication per secondment on the approved research topic. Publications can be working papers, journal articles, book chapters, policy briefs, concept papers, or similar publication.

Secondments and their accompanying deliverables take place within Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society or Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. At the onset of the secondment, in the Researcher Declaration Form, researchers indicate whether their research topic falls within WP2 or WP3. The following list of academic citations are the list of publications that PRODIGEES researchers produced within the theme of WP2. As further publications are forthcoming, including an edited volume as a main project research result, the list is not yet exhaustive. All published work from PRODIGEES is available in the project's online repository, "PRODIGEES Research Community", on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/records>

Breuer, A. (2024). *Information integrity and information pollution. Vulnerabilities and impact on social cohesion and democracy in Mexico*. IDOS Discussion Paper 2/2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Breuer, A. (2025). *From polarisation to autocratisation: The role of information pollution in Brazil's democratic erosion* (IDOS Discussion Paper 2/2025). Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS). <https://doi.org/10.23661/idp2.2025>

Čas, J. (2023). „Künstliche Intelligenz“ und soziale Nachhaltigkeit. *Ethische Prinzipien für KI-Technologien als Lösungen für die Reduktion von Armut und Ungleichheit*. Magazin erwachsenenbildung.at. Das Fachmedium für Forschung, Praxis und Diskurs 49.

Cavalcanti de Alcântara, R. (2024). *inhabiting body-territories in the datafied city. a Zine about embodiment*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14825042>

Dang, V., Bootwalla, A., Lynders, E. M. & Reiners, W. (2024). *Synergising digital public infrastructure and digital commons for sustainable development*. Mumbai: Gateway House: Indian Council on Global Relations.

Dang, V., Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2023). *Big ambition meets geopolitics. Are Southern voices and the SDGs the way to success for India's G20 presidency?* The Current Column 21 August 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

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Grimm, S., Reiners, W., & Stewart, B. (2020). *How the EU and rising powers can shape their future sustainably*. The Current Column, 6 April 2020. Bonn: German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE).

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Haegele, R. & Mansur, J. A. (2023). *Women, Water, Wi-Fi. How digitalisation and technology empower women working on the ocean and along the Amazon River*. The Current Column 19 June 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Haegele, R., & Hornidge, A. (2025). *Transnational Intersectionality at Sea: Gender, Appearance, Ethnicity, Age, and Marine Knowledge Production*. *Ocean and Society*, 2, Article 8737. <https://doi.org/10.17645/oas.8737>

Hendytio, M. K. (2025). *Think tank public communication in the digital era: The organizational aspect* (CSIS Policy Paper). Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) Indonesia.

Heuwinkel, S. & Haegele, R. (2024). *Kommunikation in der Polykrise. Was Wissenschaftskommunikation von konstruktivem Journalismus lernen kann*. The Current Column 27 March 2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Kachelmann, M. & Reiners, W. (2023). *The European Union's governance approach to tackling disinformation – protection of democracy, foreign influence, and the quest for digital sovereignty*. *L'Europe en Formation*, No 396(1), 11-36. <https://doi.org/10.3917/eufor.396.0011>.

- Kumar A. (2023). *Digitalisation for inclusive development: an overview of digital strategies and public policies in the Europe and India*. RIS Discussion Paper Series 280. New Delhi: Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS).
- Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2022, September 14). *A new era for the G20? Insights from the T20 Summit 2022 in Indonesia*. IDOS Blog.
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- van der Westhuizen, J. (2024). *Huawei or the US way? Why Brazil and South Africa did not securitize 5G*. *Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional*, 67(2).

